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EFFECTS OF PESTICIDES ON *Tetragonisca angustula* (JATAÍ BEE)

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Abstract

Bees are the main pollinating agents of greatest economic and environmental importance, recognized for the efficiency of their ecosystem service in plant species. However, the survival of bees is threatened due to the disordered use of pesticides to control pests and crop diseases. This work aimed to evaluate the effects of three pesticides (fenpyroximate, triflumizole and λ -cyhalothrin) in three routes of exposure (ingestion, topical, and contact surface) in the species *Tetragonisca angustula*. Lethality and behavioural changes were observed after 01, 06, 12, 24, 48, 72 and 96 hours for forager bees exposed to each pesticide^[1,2,3,4]. The data obtained in the experiments were subjected to Kaplan-Meier survival analysis using the R software. When in contact with λ -cyhalothrin in the ingestion route, bees did not show any significant decrease in survival (survival > 80%; $\chi^2 = 11,3$, df= 6, $p = 0,08$). However, there was a significant difference in the topical application routes and contact surface ($p < 0.05$). The sublethal effects of the exposures were also observed in all exposure routes, which had an impact on behavioural parameters such as agitation, disorientation, difficulty in locomotion, excessive wing flapping, self-cleaning, and prostration. In addition, after 24 hours of exposure to λ -cyhalothrin, the bees presented paralysis in the topical and contact surface areas. Fenpyroximate and triflumizole did not cause a significant reduction in survival ($p > 0.05$), except for exposure to triflumizole through ingestion (survival > 70%; $\chi^2 = 25,5$, df= 6, $p < 0,01$). As for λ -cyhalothrin, the behavioural impact of these two other pesticides was also observed in the three routes of exposure. The species *T. angustula* showed sensitivity to pesticides in all exposure routes, demonstrating that chemicals used in crops are harmful to non-target organisms, such as bees.

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